

OVERALL DIGITAL SERVICES CATALOGUE

[M12 VERSION – 2023-12-31]

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Document Revision History

Date	Issue	Author/Editor/Contributor	Summary of main change
2023-11-28	V1	Agnese Chiatti (POLIMI)	First document version
2023-12-18	V2	Agnese Chiatti (POLIMI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Added contributions and inputs from other partners on delivered and planned digital services: Riegler-Nurscher Peter (JR), Davaadorj Battulga and Raffaele Giaffreda (FBK), Michał Błaszczak (PSNC)- Added description of currently listed digital services for partners to review
2023-12-19	V3	Giulio Fontana (POLIMI)	Final revision

Executive summary

Deliverable D2.5 provides an overview of the current digital services offered by partners in the context of WP2 activities. Specifically, a bird's eye view analysis of the distribution of services across physical, digital and conformity-related services is provided to contextualize the larger picture surrounding the offering of digital services. Then, in Sections 2 and 3, digital services delivered as of 2023 and future/planned digital services are presented, as these will ultimately shape the implementation of the AgrifoodTEF digital infrastructure.

The current provision of digital services, i.e. those within the scope of WP2, constitutes 37% of the services in AgrifoodTEF's service catalogue. It must be noted that the separation of services into "digital", "physical" and "conformity-related", though convenient for the association of services to Work Packages, is not an element used by AgrifoodTEF for service classification or selection (Deliverable D2.1 provides a description of the chosen classification and selection methodology). As a consequence, such separation of services –useful in the context of this Deliverable– is nonetheless subject to a degree of arbitrariness and its ultimate interest is more qualitative than quantitative. While many services are easily classified as physical, digital, or conformity-related, challenges arise in classifying others. This is indeed a positive element, since it highlights how AgrifoodTEF's catalogue is evolving beyond the constraints required by the rigid format of the project proposal into a more flexible tool where services assume forms and contents that are most suitable for their users.

In some cases, the analysis done on the service catalogue prompted a reassessment of the current definition of some services, with a focus on enhancing the clarity and transparency in distinguishing between the physical and digital components of the same testing and experimentation service. For some services that admit declinations in both the physical and digital worlds, it was found that transforming their "physical" and "digital" declinations into separate services made these services clearer (and hopefully more attractive) to users.

The findings and subsequent adjustments presented in this document will contribute to a more robust and tailored approach in developing the necessary digital infrastructure, aligning with the objectives of Work Package 2. This Deliverable will be updated yearly to reflect and document the evolution of AgrifoodTEF's digital services.

1. Digital services in AgrifoodTEF's service catalogue

The objective of this analysis is identifying WP2-related services and clustering services across partners to ultimately synthesize the requirements of the future AgrifoodTEF digital infrastructure.

In a preliminary analysis of the latest service catalogue provided by Work Package 4 (version 1.1), we labelled services as **physical services**, **digital services**, or **conformity services**. All services that do not fit in these categories were marked as **other**. The resulting analysis is available for inspection in the Excel file named **2023-11-09_service_catalog_version1_1-physical+digital+conformity.xlsx**

while its outcomes are described in the following.

As a result of this analysis of the service catalogue, the following subdivision emerged:

- 88 physical services
- 77 digital services
- 17 conformity services
- 26 other services

In the following we will focus on digital (i.e., WP2-related) services, since they are the topic of this Deliverable. The current provision of digital services accounts for 37% of the total number of services, and thus accounts for a major part of the catalogue. A similar percentage corresponds to physical services, while conformity services take a smaller role in the catalogue. All this corresponds to expectations.

One interesting and partially unexpected element is the high number (26) of services that could not be unambiguously annotated as physical, digital, or conformity-related. In part this is a consequence of the way these services are described, but another reason is that the service catalogue of AgrifoodTEF –though focused on testing and experimentation– is evolving to cover additional services that support and enhance testing and experimentation activities but cannot be directly classified as such: for instance, training services supporting AgrifoodTEF customers in using testing services.

An important observation is that many among the digital services available today in the catalogue focus on providing datasets. As a result, it is anticipated that the effective management and distribution of data (including the definition of suitable access policies) will play a crucial role in shaping the future of AgrifoodTEF's digital infrastructure and in determining the necessary documentation, metadata alignment and data harmonization efforts. This corresponds to elements already evidenced by activities in tasks T2.1 and T2.2.

The analysis of the service catalogue also showed that there are services that could be annotated in multiple ways: often as both “physical” and “digital”. In many cases, this happened for services that were applicable either to physical testing or to digital testing, but that (when actually provided to a user) did not include both elements at the same time. For such services, POLIMI proposed to all project partners to evaluate if splitting them into parallel services clearly targeted to either the digital/data realm or the physical realm could improve the clarity in describing the service and, for potential users, in understanding if the service could benefit them.

To illustrate this, POLIMI and UNIMI proceeded to split all their services encompassing both digital and physical realms, making the separation between their physical and digital testing and experimentation activities more clear-cut.

A new version (1.2) of the service catalogue incorporating these changes was subsequently produced by Work Package 4.

Finally, the labeling of services as physical services, digital services, or conformity services was repeated on version 1.2 of the catalogue, and is available for inspection in the Excel file named **2023-12-18_service_catalog_version1_2-physical+digital+conformity.xlsx**

As explained, no major changes were introduced with version 1.2 of the service catalogue. The main change was the reframing of digital services offered by POLIMI and UNIMI to better discriminate between their digital and physical declinations. As a result of this decoupling, the total number of digital services slightly increased (79 digital services as opposed to 77), while the counts for the other service categories remained unchanged. The subdivision of AgrifoodTEF's service catalogue in its latest version (1.2) is therefore the following:

- 88 physical services
- 79 digital services
- 17 conformity services
- 26 other services

2. Delivered digital services

We use the term “delivered digital services” to refer to services that we identified as digital in the analysis described in Section 1 and have been provided to a customer as of 2023-12-31. We will leave the discussion of services that are in the catalogue but have not been delivered to any customers to Section 3.

In 2023, AgrifoodTEF delivered three digital services. All were provided by Josephinum Research (JR). These services are described in the [most recently updated list of services](#) (maintained by WP4) as follows:

- **S00170 AI Model Training and Benchmarking.** An existing model is trained and tested with different hyper parameters using a dataset. The model either is provided by the customer or is a well-known and public model. The dataset is provided either by the customer or by JR. It is also possible to test against existing benchmark datasets. The models are trained and tested using GPU server resources from JR.
- **S00171 Data analysis.** Use of descriptive statistics to get an insight into a dataset and statistical methods for plausibility filtering and filtering of outliers of the provided data to improve model training process.
- **S00172 Data augmentation.** Pre-processing of image or sensor data such as normalization, correlation analysis, dimension reduction, adding randomized noise and artificial expansion, as well as anonymization and data labeling.

All three services have been provided by Josephinum Research to the same company, *Blickwinkel Digital Service*¹. Blickwinkel Digital Service offers precision farming services, with a primary focus on drones. Their main use cases concern the development of AI models to detect the presence of Datura plants in a cultivation from UAV images. They required AgrifoodTEF services for testing and improving their models.

The activity of Blickwinkel Digital Service for which they used AgrifoodTEF's digital services also involves testing activities in a physical facility: since these are physical services, they will be .

¹ <https://www.blickwinkel.pro/>

3. Current and planned AgrifoodTEF digital services

This section overviews the digital services that are currently listed in the AgrifoodTEF catalogue. A few discussion pointers and ideas for future extensions of the current service offering that are envisioned by the partners of Work Package 2 are also provided. Both the present and future offering of digital services are being used by WP2 to shape the digital infrastructure supporting service provision. In the following, we organise the presentation of currently available services and future ideas by partner. Only the partners that contribute digital services to AgrifoodTEF's catalogue are considered. POLIMI and UNIMI are treated as a single service provider since they develop and execute their services jointly.

3.1 POLIMI + UNIMI

Overview of digital services currently offered. POLIMI and UNIMI's current digital services are focused on the design, setup and execution of digital testing activities, defined as the execution of experiments in a controlled digital environment with collection of data about the outcome of the experiments and application of quantitative evaluation metrics to such data.

The computing infrastructure employed for these services is currently provided by POLIMI, but a migration towards the computing resources of the AgrifoodTEF digital infrastructure is planned. The way POLIMI uses the computing infrastructure to execute digital testing for an AgrifoodTEF customer is the following:

1. POLIMI and UNIMI, together with the customer, define the (digital) experiments to be run.
2. Docker images containing the customer's own software are uploaded to the computing infrastructure.
3. The Docker images are executed in a digital test environment where the software interacts with relevant AgrifoodTEF resources (e.g., datasets) in order to perform experiments.
4. The outcomes of the experiments (i.e., output files created by the software and/or by digital test environment documenting the execution process and its results) are collected by AgrifoodTEF's digital infrastructure.
5. (If required) AgrifoodTEF executes a performance evaluation of the outcomes employing suitable metrics.
6. The customer is provided with the outcomes of the experiments and with the results of the performance evaluation.

Each element of this pipeline (experiments, digital environment, evaluation metrics) can be customised to match the requirements of the individual customer, including design and implementation *ex novo* where needed.

Digital services currently in catalogue. Current services by POLIMI and UNIMI in the latest catalogue version that can be considered as digital are:

- **S00176 - Design of computational environments for digital testing.** Items to be defined can include: design of the data (and metadata) requirements to support the test; design of software requirements to support the test, including virtual environments for running the tests; design of hardware requirements to support the test.
- **S00177 - Design of testing protocols for digital testing.** Items to be defined can include: list of datasets used for testing; descriptions of data formats and metadata standards for reproducibility; AI model selection; data pre-processing and preparation steps; parameter values and/or range.
- **S00178 - Design of evaluation metrics for the results of digital testing.** Items to be defined are the quantitative and/or qualitative performance metrics to be applied to test results.
- **S00179 - Desk assessment activities for digital systems and/or data.** Evaluation of mapping between test requirements and features of the system or data to be tested.

- **S00180 - Preparation of digital test environment.** Preparation of digital environment + preparation of technical infrastructure supporting the tests.
- **S00181 - Support in interconnecting system under test to the AgrifoodTEF computational infrastructure.** Integration of user systems and data with testing infrastructure, including the development of any additional components needed for such integration (e.g., a data format translation module).
- **S00182 - Execution of digital testing.** General support during execution of tests by the system under test (e.g., monitoring activities to ensure compliance to protocol). Technical support during execution of tests by the system under test (e.g., ensuring that the necessary processes on the system under test are correctly configured and running). Management of technical infrastructure during execution of the tests by the system under test, including verification of data exchange between system under test and infrastructure.
- **S00183 - Collection of test data during digital testing.** Collection of data generated by the system under test. Collection of data generated by agrifoodTEF's technical infrastructure relevant for the test. Curation of the documentation accompanying the collected data (e.g., description of logged features, information for test reproducibility).
- **S00184 - Evaluation of results of digital testing.** Application of performance metrics (previously defined) to test data (previously collected); delivery of evaluation results to user.

New/planned services. While POLIMI and UNIMI currently do not have any service focused on dataset provisioning in the catalogue, these are planned. At POLIMI, several different datasets for testing AI models on weeding and plant phenotyping tasks are currently available. These include RGB, RGB-D, LiDAR, RTK GPS, IMU, Near Infrared and hyperspectral imaging, as well as robot navigation and logging information, collected at various locations. POLIMI and UNIMI will provide digital services based upon this data for AI model training and for remote evaluation of the performance of AI models.

Future ideas. POLIMI and UNIMI are also discussing the possibility for future digital services to include the injection of formal knowledge representations for the improvement of the AI solutions provided by customers for monitoring the status of plants and promptly detecting any emerging diseases. The envisaged representations will describe the procedural agronomic knowledge and know-how required for image understanding and autonomous decision making. Relevant knowledge will be gathered through both reusing existing resources (e.g., ontologies in the agronomy and plant physiology domains) and eliciting missing knowledge properties from the interaction with domain experts.

POLIMI and UNIMI also intend to offer the possibility of executing the tests in a simulated environment. This would lead to decreased service cost and faster customer feedback, possibly leading to a smooth in-field transition. Closely related to this topic, the possibility of synthetic data generation services for model training is being investigated.

3.2 FBK

Overview of digital services currently offered. FBK digital services include AI algorithm performance assessment, data valorization, dataspace integration assessment, advanced weather forecasting testing, and multilingual application translation solutions. These services collectively aim to enhance agricultural technology by optimizing AI algorithms, maximizing data value, improving weather forecasting accuracy, and refining multilingual applications for the agricultural domain.

The services may include common components such as:

- **Data Analysis Tools:** Utilizing various tools for data analysis, processing, and modeling.
- **Testing Environments:** Establishing environments for testing algorithms, integrations, or solutions.
- **Consulting and Recommendations:** Providing advisory services for optimizing technology and strategy.

- Performance Metrics: Developing and evaluating metrics to assess accuracy, efficiency, and usability.
- Enhanced Integration: Focusing on seamless integration with existing agricultural systems.

Digital services currently in catalogue. Current services by FBK in the latest catalogue version that can be considered as digital are:

- **S00124 - AI algorithms performance assessment.** Support clients in defining metrics and testing their AI solutions in real life, in the field or virtually. Within normal and "stressed" operating conditions, including AI generated test cases, we assess the readiness of agriculture related AI algorithms for classification (weeds, chromatic analysis of crops), surround understanding and perception capabilities (for safety, for navigation), yield measurement (quantity of produce, quality), robotics (anomaly detection, etc.). Besides accuracy metrics, we have experience evaluating Memory and computing power footprint, and by doing so understanding bottlenecks and improving energy efficiency of proposed solutions.
- **S00125 - Data valorization and dataspace integration assessment.** Analysis of collected data in the context of AI agriculture product or service development and opportunities for data-value extraction via integration within a DataSpace. We can help customers understand the value of their data (monetary and non-monetary) and channels to offer it to potential users / buyers. By analyzing the offer and demand in relevant Data Spaces, we suggest the optimal way to describe metadata and adopt the right technology implementations to make data visible ensuring data-owners never loose control of who accesses their data. The services include consulting customers on the enrichment of their data system to adopt data sovereignty and trust solutions that makes them contribute-to and be part-of the European data space strategy.

New/planned services. Planned digital services to extend the aforementioned offering include:

- **Testing Integration and performance of advanced weather forecasting.** Solutions in the Agricultural sector that use weather forecasts can suffer from inaccuracies of standard weather service APIs, such as lack of granularity, no usage of in-field sensors, low precision of generic models. Using FBK's expertise in advanced weather forecasting we are capable of testing weather related functionalities in solutions and propose ways forward to take it to the next level: nowcasting, higher resolution, model optimization for specific regions, etc.
- **Testing of translation solutions for multilingual applications.** Agriculture is a local and specific business, where localization of solutions is required, especially when it comes to language and interfacing with users. Albeit the diffusion of multilingual generative AI technologies (or Large Language Models, e.g. GPT), these models are not optimized for a specific industry. We can test the performance of multilingual AI solutions in Agriculture and analyze how to improve their performance. This allows for optimized localization of solutions and quicker achievement of scalability at the European level.

3.3 PSNC

Digital services currently in catalogue. Current services by PSNC in the latest catalogue version that can be considered as digital are:

- **S00049 AI Integration - Data Storage.** Provide data storage infrastructure for AI, simulations and data processing results.
- **S00050 AI Integration - V-Server / PaaS / AI platform.** Provide virtual infrastructure Cloud Virtual Servers/PaaS/ AI Platform to support deployment of the models/tools/software stack.

- **S00051 AI Integration - Computation Power.** Provide HPC and Grid-Computing infrastructure for AI, simulations and data processing.

New/planned services. PSNC's planned digital services to be added to the next catalogue iterations will cover the areas listed below. Because these are planned digital services, their implementation is still to be decided.

- **AI Integration - Model Improvement/Adaptation.** Support for improving existing models/algorithms/software with on-field data acquisition, e.g., on-field data weed detection and biomass estimation.
- **AI integration – Algorithms.** Provide support for the integration of AI algorithms in agro-food systems/machines. Integration will be adjusted with available data interfaces and communication standards.
- **AI Integration - Predictive System.** Assist in developing a predictive system for arable crops.
- **Datasets – Benchmark.** Provide benchmark training data sets incl. labels and metadata for benchmarking AI algorithms by the target groups. Datasets will be configured or adjusted individually according to the needs of the customer, within field operations, technological processes or communication.
- **High-Value-Testfield – Usability / UX.** Provide usability and user experience (UX) evaluation on AI-based tools for high-value crops, e.g., vineyards.
- **Robotic Integration – Algorithms.** Provide support for the integration of autonomous robots in agro-food domains/subdomains.
- **Testing – Cybersecurity.** Provide pre-certification testing of the cybersecurity of AI products by, e.g., pentests and vulnerability scans.

3.4 LNE

Digital services currently in catalogue. Current services by LNE in the latest catalogue version that can be considered as digital are:

- **S00082 - Dataset provision for weed detection.** Provision of data set of plant/weed pictures for weed detection.
- **S00083 - Automatic machines and Agricultural robots. Virtual testing: New Safety function tests** (ARPA 1 anti-collision and ARPA 3 geofencing).
- **S00084 - Automatic machines and Agricultural robots. virtual testing: Performance qualification** (mobility, energy, etc.).
- **S00085 - Automatic machines and Agricultural robots. virtual testing: High-level supervision tasks** (homogeneous and heterogeneous robots cooperation, communication links, etc.).
- **S00086 - Automatic machines and Agricultural robots. virtual testing: Advanced tools** (remote monitoring, database creation for deep learning phase of AI systems, preventive maintenance)
- **S00087 - Dataset provision – general.** Provision of data set for testing or training (various media and content).
- **S00088 - Dataset quality assessment.** Assessment of the quality of a given dataset (to be used for training or testing of an AI system).
- **S00089 - AI performance evaluation based on testing datasets.** Tests of AI software module based on a datasets. The test consists in comparing the outputs of the system with a dataset of reference values.
- **S00090 - Automatic machines and Agricultural robots. Provision of learning and testing datasets for experimentation and evaluation of AI technologies in viticulture: Image datasets for the autonomous detection of disease (mildew) and health/vigor/water status of vines.**

- **S00091 - Automatic machines and Agricultural robots. Provision of learning and testing datasets for experimentation and evaluation of AI technologies in viticulture: Image datasets for the autonomous detection of weeds.**
- **S00092 - Automatic machines and Agricultural robots. Provision of learning and testing datasets for experimentation and evaluation of AI technologies in viticulture: Meteorological sensors datasets.**
- **S00094 - AI robustness evaluation based on testing datasets.** Evaluation of the robustness of the AI software module, i.e. its capacity to present the right outputs in all foreseeable normal conditions of operation.
- **S00095 - AI resilience evaluation.** Evaluation of the resilience of the AI software module, i.e. its capacity to present adapted outputs in all foreseeable anomalous conditions of operation.

Future ideas. Future extensions of the digital services listed above may include the provision of simulation environments for testing that will build on autonomous driving settings but will be specifically tailored to the AgrifoodTEF context. The simulation would support weed detection scenarios for instance, but additional scenarios will be considered/explored based also on the offering of other partners and on the recognised added value. In addition to the dataset provision that already characterises LNE's offering in support to weed detection tasks, several different visual detection scenarios will be considered in the context of dataset provision services.

3.5 RISE

Overview of digital services currently offered. Current services offered by RISE that can be categorised as digital are listed in the following. It is worth noting that these services also include physical testing components in addition to those strictly pertaining to digital testing.

Digital services currently in catalogue. Current services by RISE in the latest catalogue version that can be considered as digital are:

- **S00013 - Experimentation AI Crop production.** Experiment on robotic and AI solutions for agriculture. Dependent on the specific needs a company has, the service is adjusted to fulfil the needs.
- **S00014 - Experimentation AI Livestock production.** Experiment on robotic and AI solutions for agriculture. Dependent on the specific needs a company has, the service is adjusted to fulfil the needs.
- **S00015 - Experimentation Robotics Crop production.** Experiment on robotic and AI solutions for agriculture. Dependent on the specific needs a company has, the service is adjusted to fulfil the needs.
- **S00016 - Experimentation Robotics Livestock production.** Experiment on robotic and AI solutions for agriculture. Dependent on the specific needs a company has, the service is adjusted to fulfil the needs.
- **S00017 - Experimentation UAV Crop production.** Experiment on robotic and AI solutions for agriculture. Dependent on the specific needs a company has, the service is adjusted to fulfil the needs.
- **S00018 - Experimentation UAV Livestock production.** Experiment robotic and AI solutions for agriculture. Dependent on the specific needs a company has, the service is adjusted to fulfil the needs.
- **S00022 - Virtual training or validation of crop and weed detection.** RISE openWeeds database is under development and can be used for training and validation of weed detection machine learning algorithms. The annotated images are captured in RISE agrifood testbed and contain some of the weeds growing in the nordic environment.
- **S00030 - Expand training datasets by using synthetic data based on existing datasets.** Together with company develop methodology for expanding training dataset with synthetic data.

Future ideas. From the other AI-related services composing RISE's offering, plans are being made to adapt these to the AgrifoodTEF area.

3.6 ILVO

Digital services currently in catalogue. Current services by ILVO in the latest catalogue version that can be considered as digital are:

- **S00005 Food consumption analysis.** Food waste detection, food consumption analyses for nutritional defects analysis
- **S00006 Agri Dataset Generation.** Automated agricultural generated datasets and model validation datasets.

3.7 JR

Digital services currently in catalogue. Current services by JR in the latest catalogue version that can be considered as digital are:

- **S00041 - Providing dataset for training purposes.** provide specific datasets for training ML (images, sensor data, ...)
- **S00042 - Providing benchmark dataset.** provide specific datasets for benchmarking ML (images, sensor data, ...)
- **S00170 – AI model training.** Guided training of machine learning models via GPU server resources from JR.
- **S00171 - Data analysis.** Use of descriptive statistics to get an insight into a dataset and statistical methods for plausibility filtering and filtering of outliers of the provided data to improve model training process.
- **S00172 - Data augmentation.** Pre-processing of image or sensor data such as normalization, correlation analysis, dimension reduction, adding randomized noise and artificial expansion, as well as anonymization and data labeling.

3.8 RGRD

Digital services currently in catalogue. Current services by RGRD in the latest catalogue version that can be considered as digital are:

- **S00036 – datasets.** Data set provision

3.9 INRAE

Overview of digital services currently offered. Current services in the latest catalogue version that can be considered as digital include:

- **S00072 - Virtual ARPA test - Level 1:** Exploitation of new tools for generation of Synthetic realistic data sets to test AI systems based on camera sensors - Application to ARPA4. Generation of huge simulated realistic scenes representative of various working conditions from one original image (2D OR 3D, static OR Dynamic). Exploitation: (i) for learning phase of IA Systems; (ii) for testing efficiency of AI Systems.
- **S00073 – Virtual ARPA test - Level 2:** Exploitation of Digital twins for virtual test activities about safety and other robotic performances assessments. Development in progress of a complementary digital twin for safety tests of agricultural robots.

- **S00075 - Virtual weeding solution test - Level 1: Exploitation of news tools for generation of Synthetic realistic data sets to test AI systems based on camera sensors - Application to weed destruction systems evaluation.** Generation of huge simulated realistic scenes representative of various working conditions from one original image (2D OR 3D, static OR Dynamic).

3.10

IFV

Digital services currently in catalogue. Current services by IFV in the latest catalogue version that can be considered as digital are:

- **S00102 - Provision of datasets for AI training in real vinegrowing conditions.**
- **S00104 - Data labelling for AI detection purposes in the vineyard.** Give support and expertise on data labelling in real vinegrowing conditions.
- **S00105 - Data analysis for AI performance evaluation in a real vineyard.** Helps to validate the outcomes of an AI solution in the field.
- **S00148 - Datasets and infrastructure for automatic monitoring of daily individual liveweight in small ruminants.** Providing huge, historic, structured datasets and physical facilities under experimental conditions for testing AI solutions for developing Early Warning Systems (EWS) for small ruminants under a large spectrum of conditions. Interconnect Gold Standards and datasets. Provision of living animals (small ruminants, sheep), experimental facilities, and real-time sensor data (WoW platform) to evaluate AI systems in real farming conditions. Experimental facilities for small ruminants (sheep) including indoor and outdoor (harsh) conditions. Walk-over-Weighing (WoW) platform for real-time automatic monitoring of individual liveweight. Static scale (ISO ref.), reference datasets gathered under controlled conditions. results: Real-time EWS for individual welfare, performance and health.
- **S00149 - Eggs detection.** Dataset of annotated images where parasite eggs are located. The location of eggs was manually annotated on thousands of microscope images. This dataset can be used to train a neural network able to automatically count the number of eggs on picture. This could have the application to estimate the level of infestation of animals. Coproscopy is particularly time consuming, automatic method could be very helpful. Images from microscope were manually annotated to locate the eggs.
- **S00150 – Goat detection.** Dataset of annotated images where animals are located. This dataset could be used to train a neural network specialized in outdoor goat detections. This network can then be used instead of a GPS (more costly and one sensor per animal vs 1 camera for all animals).
- **S00151 - Behavior via accelerometers.** Data set of annotated sequences of 3 Axis acceleration data with the associated behavior. This dataset could be used to train an algorithm to estimate behavior from accelerometers data. Animals were set up with accelerometers and film to annotate their behavior. In total, hours of film were annotated. Dataset is still in development.
- **S00152 - Provision of datasets for AI training: photo and video.** Provision of structured and well described datasets. This dataset can be used in conjunction with another complementary dataset (e.g. health, feed intake).
- **S00153 - Provision of datasets for AI training: feed intake datasets.** Provision of structured and well described datasets. This dataset can be used in conjunction with another complementary dataset (e.g. health, photo, video).
- **S00154 - Provision of datasets for AI training: health datasets.** Provision of structured and well described datasets. This dataset can be used in conjunction with another complementary dataset (e.g. feed intake, photo, video).

- **S00155 - Provision of a virtual computing infrastructure.** Virtual computing infrastructure (CPU, GPU) and storage space.

3.11 WUR

Digital services currently in catalogue. Current WUR services that also consist of digital components, in addition to physical aspects of testing, are:

- **S00127 - Test, validation and data collection of Robotic and AI systems and components for arable farming solutions.** Test, validation and data collection of Robotic and AI systems and components for arable farming solutions on the Farms of the Future, including collecting ground truth data sets.
- **S00130 - Test, validation and data collection of Robotic and AI systems and components for livestock farming solutions on Farm of the Future.** Test, validation and data collection of Robotic and AI systems and components for livestock farming solutions on the Farms of the Future (De Marke), including collecting ground truth data sets
- **S00132 - Test, validation and data collection of Robotic and AI systems and components for livestock farming solutions on the Farms of the Future (De Marke), including collecting ground truth data sets.** Data sets are available for development or validation of AI algorithms.
- **S00133 - Data analysis support for specific and long-term data sets for arable and livestock farming data sets.** Advice is available for analysis of large and multiple sources data sets.
- **S00136 - Provision of Farmmaps platform to support Precision farming and KPI accounting data services.** Access to farm data within code of conduct farm data use via global WUR platform www.farmmaps.eu, with access to open data and farming data.
- **S00143 - Provision of Agro Data Cube platform for data handling.** AgroDataCube provides a large collection of both open data and derived data for use in agri-food applications and aims to become a common reference point for data rich applications in agriculture, where it has been set up with a focus on agricultural production and its environmental performance.

3.12 ARVALIS

Digital services currently in catalogue. Current services by ARVALIS in the latest catalogue version that can be considered as digital are:

- **S00159 - Evaluation of Smart Perception Systems for Precision Farming: agrophotonic sensors.** Test and development of agrophotonic sensors & image processing chains. Acquisition and interpretation of image datasets acquired through sensors, to generate agronomic indicators (LAI, biomass, number of plants etc...)
- **S00160 - Evaluation of Smart Perception Systems for Precision Farming: satellite data.** Test and development of satellite image interpretation models. Provision of performance evaluation of models integrating satellite images for yield estimation, supply chains, pre-harvest grain quality/risk estimation, from satellite data.
- **S00166 - Dataset provision for weed detection. Provision of dataset of plant/weed pictures for weed detection.** Provision of learning and testing dataset for experimentation and evaluation of AI technologies.

4. Conclusions

The goal of this Deliverable is to describe the current state of AgrifoodTEF's digital services, i.e. those that are closely related to the activities of Work Package 2.

The first part of the document provided an analysis of the service offering in the catalogue. We labeled the services in the two most recent versions of the AgrifoodTEF catalogue (v1.1 and v1.2) to discriminate between “physical services”, “digital services”, “conformity-related services”, and services that cannot be unequivocally labeled in any of these ways. We found that 79 (i.e., ~37%) out of the services currently offered can be considered “digital”.

This analysis also provided insights about possible improvements to the services to improve clarity for users and ease in finding relevant services.

The second part of Deliverable D2.5 describes the digital services delivered to customers by AgrifoodTEF in 2023. Since this has been the first year of the project, the number of delivered services is still low.

The third part of the document is an overview of the output of AgrifoodTEF partners involved in offering digital service. For each partner, we described:

- services that are already in the catalogue;
- services that the partner plans to add to the catalogue;
- (if any) ideas that the partner is exploring about new services to be designed.

The contents of Deliverable D2.5 are relevant not only to provide information about the current state and evolution of the digital services, but also to shape the development of AgrifoodTEF’s digital infrastructure that will support them. Work Package 2 includes many ongoing activities focused on this development. The digital infrastructure does not correspond to mere hardware: other tasks that interact synergistically with the design of the envisioned infrastructure concern, for instance, the definition of dataspace for AgrifoodTEF and the definition of adequate data harmonization and documentation tools supporting the infrastructure.

Although the service catalogue of AgrifoodTEF is maintained by Work Package 4, this document provides a snapshot of the state of digital services and includes outcomes from recent discussions and brainstorming sessions with partners in the WP2 periodic meetings.

